

A PROPOSED CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE ONE STOP SHOP FOR THE JOBSEEKERS OF CALOOCAN CITY – SOUTH

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ABSTRACT

As the Philippines is shifting from the traditional public administration practices and theories that relied highly on a centralized way of governance, this study attempted to give breath to a long-standing approach to public administration practices that decentralizes service delivery and extends capacity building to local government units. The study situated itself in Caloocan City – South where there is an estimate of 7,000 jobseekers per DOLE's data. It explored the creation of a conceptual framework on a One Stop Shop (OSS) for jobseekers as a response to the growing concerns of jobseekers in securing their pre-employment requirements. As discovered in this study, jobseekers, in general, are wanting a more accessible location for those national agencies, such as SSS, NBI, PhilHealth, Pagibig, BIR, PSA from whom the needed requirements are to be applied for and processed. The jobseekers believed that a single location for all these agencies shall provide them with convenience in terms of time and movement, and certainly, would cut down their expenses. Using the descriptive research approach, the study found the potential of the city government of Caloocan City, having experienced a six-year long operation of BOSS (Business One Stop Shop), to establish another One Stop Shop, this time for the jobseekers.

Keywords: *One Stop Shop, Management, Philippines, Jobseekers, LGU*

INTRODUCTION

It is inevitable to any Filipino who belongs to the poor to middle class that after graduation they would go out and seek employment. While for others, they just want to move from one career to another or from one employer to a new one. It is a requirement for jobseekers to secure the necessary documents for employment whether you have worked for years or just got out of college.

In the Philippines, there are government agencies mandated by law to process and release the said documents. These agencies are Social Security System (SSS), Philippine Health Insurance Corporation (PhilHealth), Pag-Ibig Fund, Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR), and National Bureau Investigation (NBI). These national agencies are situated in various parts of the metropolis that impel jobseekers to travel from one agency to another in securing these pre-employment requirements. Their travel time would take some 30 minutes to 1 hour to go to one agency then move to another. Hence, for the 6 agencies involved, a jobseeker needs to allot an average of four hours' commute time. In addition, such travel causes unnecessary expenses in commuting to these different agencies.

Moreover, transaction time in one agency alone would take 45 minutes to 1 hour depending on the number of people transacting and queuing time involved in securing the documents. Thus, a jobseeker spends some 6 hours on this purpose.

The foregoing situation has posed difficulties for the jobseekers of the City of Caloocan South. This study has taken interest in Caloocan City as the locale of the Research because of its strategic position in the National Capital Region (NCR). Divided in two large areas — the North and South — it was the latter area that was made as the point of interest because it holds different entry points to other key places such as Quezon City, Bulacan, Valenzuela and Manila. Data gathered from the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) informs that the labor force participation of Caloocan City is at 63.2%. This is relatively low given that the local economy of the city is anchored in various service and manufacturing industries.

This research project then defined its first objective of exploring the jobseekers' situation in securing their pre-employment requirements. What was earlier described was perceived and observed by this researcher based on a few information gathered. In addition, it was also discovered that the Labor Code of the Philippines provides for the promotion of equal rights and opportunities. Following this policy, if the State is unable to effect services that are accessible, convenient, and timely, the jobseekers' opportunity to meet their livelihood aspirations may be jeopardized. It may be an individual and personal loss, but it has a ripple effect on the country's socio-economic progress. Jobseekers' lost opportunity for work adds to unemployment problems that could lead to a possible slowdown of the economy.

Relevant Provisions of Republic Act 11261

The Philippines has a law that waives payment of fees on the processing and issuance of government documents necessary for employment of fresh graduates or first-time jobseekers. This is Republic Act No. 11261 passed on April 10, 2019 and its Section 4 specifically stipulates: No fees and other charges shall be collected from first time jobseekers when obtaining the following: (a) police clearance certificate; (b) National Bureau of Investigation clearance; (c) barangay clearance; (d) medical certificate from a public hospital, except the fees and charges collected for needed laboratory tests and other medical procedures; (e) birth certificate; (f) marriage certificate; (g) transcript of academic records issued by state colleges and universities; (h) tax identification number (TIN); (i) unified multi-purpose ID (UMID) card; and (j) other documentary requirements issued by the government that may be required by employers (Official Gazette of the Philippines, 2019).

Further, Section 7 of the law also stated the establishment of One Stop Shop (OSS) through the Public Employment Service Office or PESO existing in the different provinces, cities, and municipalities who shall assist first-time jobseekers in securing the required pre-employment documents from relevant government agencies. This law that should be the backbone in delivering the efficient, fast and reliable service in securing pre-employment requirements is not yet being implemented and institutionalized in Caloocan City.

At present, there is already a One Stop Shop available in Caloocan City. However, its services are only limited to renewal of business permits. This study has taken the lead to explore also the possibility of upscaling the level of playing field for a One Stop Shop to be established in the city that assists the jobseekers in securing their pre-employment requirements.

The Idea of One Stop Shop

This section presents some ideas about One Stop Shop found in certain studies for the purpose of clarifying what its concept is all about enabling this research to its intended objectives.

Segal (2019, para. 1) defined a One Stop Shop as “a firm that offers a multitude of products or services to its customers, all under one roof, so to speak. A One Stop Shop can refer to a literal roof—a specific physical location where all the business a client needs can be carried out—or it can refer to a company that handles a variety of goods or services.”

While a study conducted by Price Water Coopers (2012) informs that adopting a One Stop Shop should be holistic in approach, that is, it is anchored on citizen centric service. The study stated that “to adopt citizen-centric service delivery models can significantly improve the customer experience by delivering outcomes based on citizens’ needs,

expectations and preferences, in addition to outcomes through enhanced service levels at the same or reduced cost” (p.4).

Considering jobseekers’ situation at present and knowing the opportunity for establishing a One Stop Shop, it appeared to this researcher that the promotion and implementation of such a mechanism with an innovative approach by adopting a citizen centric delivery of services becomes imperative. The principle of good governance imparts that the delivery of services to the people must be efficient and effective in addition to promoting openness and transparency, rule of law, sound financial management, accountability, and others (Tatarenko, 2015). This author explained that principles of good governance can help public managers measure and improve the quality of their governance and enhance service delivery to citizens. In view of this, it appeared significantly necessary for local government units to adapt and cater for a better and reliable delivery of transactions relative to pre-employment requirements.

Jobseekers are struggling to secure pre-employment requirements. The distance of government agencies mandated to provide said requirements stretches the mobility of jobseekers coupled by additional transportation costs. This is the scenario that local government units like Caloocan City could respond to by way of expanding their present OSS to include services for the jobseekers in securing their pre-employment requirements.

The study of Blackburn (2015) discussed the shift of government service delivery in Tasmania to a customer-oriented style, which became a good factor in improving the relationship between the government and the community. Blackburn wrote that the Tasmanian Government’s strategy of using information technologies and private sector style business administration designed a new outlook in service delivery through their integrated whole-of-government approach.

While researchers, Janenova and Kim (2016), pointed out the implementation and significance of a One Stop Shop in Kazakhstan was discussed. In said OSS, public services such as legal, land, tax, health services, and social services were being given in a single place rather than in different scattered offices. This policy of service integration was aimed at improving the quality of services and at reducing the cases of corruption in government. The researchers have noted that there was a positive progress in improving the accessibility of public services.

Solidifying the use of One Stop Shop in other countries is supported by the research of Illsley, Llyod, and Lynch (2010) who suggested that in delivering a customer focused planning service, a One Stop Shop is deemed appropriate as a development model. In England and Scotland, it is integrated as an administrative model with defined responsibilities and relations to departments in the planning and development service.

A research conducted by the International Labour Office or ILO (2016) in Mongolia highlighting the positive impact of OSS on its population. The study showed that over 60% of the country’s populations are using the OSS on a regular basis. Using survey

covering 31 established OSSs that served more than 1.8 million customers (600,000 in Ulaanbaatar city and over 1.2 million customers in the rural areas), it received an 85% satisfaction rate. This ILO's study was intended to find out if Mongolia's One Stop Shops are accessible, transparent, and an efficient public service delivery.

The foregoing situation defined for this study the following as its objectives, namely:

1. To find out from the jobseekers themselves the difficulties they faced as they secure the needed pre-employment requirements, including the factors that have caused the difficulties;
2. To know if the establishment of a One Stop Shop would provide easy access and conveniently facilitate processing of pre-employment requirements; and
3. To gather information valuable to designing and establishing a One Stop Shop for assisting jobseekers in the acquisition of their pre-employment requirements.

Research Questions

From these objectives, the research questions outlined and guided this study were, as follows:

1. What difficulties are commonly experienced by jobseekers in securing their pre-employment requirements?
2. How can the establishment of a One Stop Shop resolve the difficulties of jobseekers in securing pre-employment requirements?
3. How can a One Stop Shop conveniently facilitate the acquisition of pre-employment requirements?

METHODOLOGY

The methodology used to know the situation of the jobseekers of Caloocan – South in securing their pre-employment requirements. Similarly, the experience of Caloocan's Business Permits and Licensing Office in operating its BOSS was solicited coupled by the "voices" of its clients to relate their experiences with the intent of this study to create a possible OSS for jobseekers in the city of Caloocan – South.

Research Design

The study took the descriptive research approach and used the inductive analysis in examining the data gathered that assisted in establishing the commonalities and correlations among the responses of the respondents. The descriptive research approach, as used in this study, has provided the extent to which the conditions of each set of target respondents have been given befitting descriptions based on the information they supplied.

Participants and Sampling Technique

There were three sets of participants in the study. The first group consisted of jobseekers residing in Caloocan city – South. They were not pre-selected as they were the respondents to the online survey. The only criterion indicated in the survey is that they are currently seeking employment. The second participant was The Business Permits and Licensing Office (BPLO) of Caloocan City, the office in charge of the Business One Stop Shop or BOSS. the respondent, occupies the position of Attorney II and the service provider in said office. While the third group was composed of three respondents representing the business sector of the city who are regular clients of BOSS. The latter were selected based on their company's size, small-scale, medium-scale, and large-scale businesses in the City of Caloocan - South. Since they requested for anonymity, they are identified in this study as Client A, Client B, and Client C. The following short descriptions of the clients:

Client A - Female, 35 years old, representing a small-scale enterprise, has experienced BOSS for some 5 years.

Client B – Male, 40 years old, representing a medium-scale enterprise, has experienced BOSS for some 3 years.

Client C – Male, 45 years old, representing a large-scale enterprise, has experienced BOSS for some 5 years.

Data Gathering Procedure

As a qualitative study using the descriptive research approach, the researcher opted to get primary data from different sources, referring to the target participants identified. The procedure in data collection was done in two stages using the instruments of online survey and Key Informant Interview (KII).

First Stage: Online Survey

The first stage made use of online surveys enjoining the jobseekers of Caloocan City – South to participate. An online technology was used by means of launching an online survey via survey monkey and google survey to reach out to different jobseekers residing within the target location. The survey questionnaire was developed containing questions that elicited the jobseekers' experience in securing their pre-employment requirements. This questionnaire was first reviewed by the adviser of this paper. Her recommendations as to format and additional questions were inputted, then the same questionnaire was reviewed by two experts on qualitative research.

These experts' review brought out these suggestions:

1. To give a bracket for the age ranges of respondents to simplify the results of the study.
2. "Name" could be deleted since the main interest of the survey is the responses of the respondents; soliciting their names is unnecessary.
3. To increase the transportation expenses of the jobseekers since the average cost of travelling to the six agencies is to be taken as a whole and not individually.
4. To delete the "barangay" where the respondent is residing as it is insignificant to ask since this research is not a case study.

These suggestions were integrated into the final draft of the survey questionnaire prior to the conduct of its pilot testing for the purpose of validation. This pilot testing were 10 respondents personally handpicked by the researcher to answer the survey questionnaire. The respondents came from varied educational backgrounds, and ages ranged from 24 years old to 28 years old. There were six males and four females who participated in this pilot test.

The results of the pilot testing revealed that on average, the survey questionnaire could be accomplished in 2 to 3 minutes. Respondents have easily accessed the online survey and have followed the instructions provided therein. The results of the pilot test informed this researcher that the questionnaire is appropriately formulated, and the use of online surveys is an efficient instrument in doing surveys, enabling the research process to produce the expected output. Likewise, it was noted that a respondent can only use this online survey once; he/she can no longer access it once his/her accomplished questionnaire has been submitted. This system then avoided repetition of the same respondent. This is a welcome development for the researcher as it ensures the avoidance of discrepancy and errors in data gathering.

Further, the researcher noted that there were no outliers in the results of the pilot test particularly related to the amenability of the creation of the OSS for jobseekers. The positive results of the pilot testing allowed this researcher to proceed to the actual online survey. This online survey initially targeted 210 respondents and ended with 253 respondents for a period of two weeks. From the current population provided by the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) from the Public Employment Service Office or (PESO) that there are approximately 7,000 jobseekers in Caloocan City - South. Using a purposive quota sampling, the researcher opted to get at least 210 respondents for the online survey. This number of respondents served as the sample population of the study.

Second Stage: Key Informant Interview

The second stage of data collection was conducted using the Key Informant Interview or KII. There were two groups of respondents interviewed. The first one was the Focal Person of the One Stop Shop in Caloocan City – South. The second group was composed

of company representatives who regularly avail of the services of Caloocan's BOSS. They are identified in this study as Client A, Client B, and Client C.

The guide questions used in interviewing Caloocan's BOSS focal Person are the following:

1. What are the factors you considered in establishing a One Stop Shop that caters to business and construction permits?
2. Why is there a need for a One Stop Shop more than the factors mentioned?
3. What were the steps you underwent in establishing the One Stop Shop?
4. What are the challenges in establishing the One Stop Shop?
5. Is there a framework that you follow that would serve as a blueprint in running the One Stop Shop?
6. What are the past and present learnings you gained in running the One Stop Shop?
7. Do you think it would be helpful to have an OSS that would cater to jobseekers' need for securing pre-employment requirements? Why or why not?
8. What are the steps one must undergo for an OSS for jobseekers becomes a reality?

These guide questions were also reviewed by qualitative research experts approached.

The second part of the KII was done with select clients of BPLO's BOSS who are experienced in processing their companies' requirements in business permits/renewals. These three clients represent a small enterprise, a medium-scale company, and the third one came from a large company in the city. Only one main question was asked to these respondents: "How will you describe your experience in renewing your business licenses at BPLO's BOSS?"

The process of this key informant interview with those involved participants was basically facilitated as a free-wheeling discussion where unstructured and open-ended questions were pitched in by this researcher to help in clarifying and amplifying respondents' answers.

Data Analysis Procedure

For data analysis, the inductive analysis was used in this study following the schema provided in Figure 1.0.

First, data gathered from the two instruments used in data collection, that is, from the online survey among the jobseekers in Caloocan city – South, and the interviews conducted with key informants, were then transcribed and consolidated for easy review by the researcher. Then, these consolidated materials were read and reread for the purpose of familiarization. At the same time, observations and the results of the data collection were started to be formulated to understand the nature of the data (Smith, 2020). This process enabled the researcher to extract initial commonalities or correlations among responses given by the respondents. Eventually, patterns or trends were

identified. Other valuable insights and ideas were also noted that have provided meaningful interpretations of the information collected.

Further, insights derived from a careful study of data sets, particularly from the KII, assisted in establishing a clear connection to the proposed conceptual framework for an OSS for jobseekers. Thus, a final framework is recommended. The data collected, consolidated, and examined were helpful in answering the research questions.

Figure 1.0
Inductive Analysis Framework

RESULTS

This contains the results of this study that used the descriptive research approach to respond to the research questions: (a) What difficulties are commonly experienced by jobseekers in securing their pre-employment requirements? (b) How can the establishment of a One Stop Shop resolve the difficulties of jobseekers in securing pre-employment requirements? (c) How can a One Stop Shop conveniently facilitate the acquisition of pre-employment requirements?

The presentation of the results of this study is organized following the instruments used in data collection. It begins with the summarized data solicited from the online survey and then from the KII.

This study has also intended to pick up the data summarized and from the discussions the elements necessary to finalize the framework conceived for Caloocan's OSS for jobseekers.

This closes with the answers to the research questions.

Results of the Online Survey

The results of the online survey presented cover the main questions of commuting expense and travelling time of respondent, transaction period of documentary requirements, and the respondent's opinion on the advantage of having an OSS for jobseekers and its potential in easily facilitating the acquisition of pre-employment requirements.

There were a total 253 respondents to the online survey. From the responses on the basic information about the respondents, all of them are currently looking for a job, and all are residents of Caloocan – South from the barangays covering Sangandaan, Grace Park – West and East, Poblacion, Dagat-Dagatan, C-3 Road – Kaunlaran Village, Maypajo, Marulas, PNR Compound, Sta. Quitera, Talipapa, and Libis. The respondents' ages range from 18 years old to 35 years old.

The bulk of the respondents, equivalent to 144 or 56.9% of the sample population, are college graduates, while vocational graduates comprised 96 or 37.9%. Some 13 respondents or 5.1% are masteral or doctoral degree holders. It was noted in the results of the survey that 150 or 59% of the respondents are employed but are looking for a new job. While the fresh graduates numbered 90 or 36%, and the unemployed accounted for only 13 or 5%.

Main Queries of the Questionnaire

As earlier mentioned, the main queries in the online survey questionnaire touched on cost and time of travelling spent by the jobseeker, the duration for transacted documents are accomplished by concerned national agencies, and the respondent's opinions on the establishment of an OSS for jobseekers.

The following summarizes the responses of the respondents to the online survey:

Transportation Cost. All of the 253 respondents or 100% admitted that it is costly to travel from one national agency to another to secure the needed pre-employment documentary requirements. On the average, an amount of P200 may be spent by a jobseeker as transportation cost. This average cost was deduced from the following answers given by the respondents: 149 jobseekers or 58.9% said they need to allot at least 70 to 120 pesos, while 101 jobseekers or 39.9% would allot a commuting expense of at least 150 to 200 pesos, and 3 other respondents have stated 220 pesos, 245 pesos, and 260 pesos, respectively, as their commuting expenses.

Travel Time. A jobseeker transacts with six national agencies, namely: SSS, Philhealth, Paglbig, NBI, PSA, BIR, to secure his/her needed documentary requirements for employment. Based on the responses to the survey, 241 out of the 253 respondents or 95.2% said that it takes them 5 to 7 hours to travel from one national agency to another, while 10 out of the 253 respondents or 4% said that it would take them 3 to 4 hours to arrive at one agency and then move to the other different agencies, and only 2 or 0.8% recognized that it would take them a travel time of 1 to 2 hours to move from one agency to another.

Transaction Period. It is a normal routine for many government transactions to be made; a client has to allot either time or days for the transactions to be accomplished. Jobseekers are aware of this; thus, the online survey has asked respondents' answers on the period (days specifically) allotted to enable them to finish all the documentary requirements for pre-employment. Here are the consolidated responses given: 4

jobseekers said that it takes 2 to 4 days for them to finish the transaction from one agency to another; 15 jobseekers said it would take them a longer period, that is, 5 to 7 days; while 234 jobseekers said that it would take them 2 weeks to transact from one agency to another.

Benefits of an OSS from Jobseekers' Perspective

The online survey has also solicited from the respondents the ways or benefits that they, as jobseekers, would gain from a One Stop Shop servicing their needs for pre-employment. The answers consolidated were, as follows: 5 jobseekers said that it would be helpful for them if the national agencies are located in one strategic area, another 5 respondents said it would be helpful for them if it would provide convenience in terms of time, 4 respondents said that the OSS should be able to promote cost- efficiency, while the rest of the 249 respondents agreed that the OSS for jobseekers should be accessible, should be able to provide convenience in terms of time, and therefore, could promote in them cost efficiency.

One Stop Shop: A Helpful Solution

The results of the online survey showed that 88% of the respondents support the idea of having a One Stop Shop, while 12% of these 254 jobseekers do not recognize that an OSS would be a solution to certain difficulties they confront in their process of securing their pre-employment requirements.

Results of the Key Informant Interview

Interview with the Focal Person of BPLO's BOSS

The results of this interview provided the information that the city of Caloocan – South was able to formulate, integrate, and implement the BOSS by complying with the recommendation of DILG through its Joint DILG-DTI Administrative Order No. 10-07 (Guidelines in Implementing the Nationwide Upscaling of Reforms in Processing Business Permits and Licenses in all Cities and Municipalities in the Philippines) enjoining all LGUs in the country to provide a “business-friendly” environment by establishing BOSS for business and licensing permits. Under these guidelines, the city government of Caloocan took the challenge and established its BOSS in 2015 with the help of different key offices and employees of the LGU and worked hand in hand to build the manpower resources, the process flow, and other services needed for said program to be fully functional.

Two important factors were drawn by the researcher as noted by the interviewee for the operation of the BOSS to be successful. The first one is close coordination with the different stakeholders of BOSS, and second is cooperation among all involved.

These two determined factors were emphatically mentioned since one of the challenges that BOSS encountered was the irregularity of the presence of some officers/staff to man

their respective areas. To resolve the situation, the city mayor released a memorandum to all concerned offices to strictly abide by implementing guidelines of the BOSS.

The interviewee also believes that an OSS for jobseekers will be a valuable assistance to these clients for it will greatly help them in securing easy pre-employment requirements. The focal person expounded by saying that an OSS for jobseekers could ease up the long and tedious process of securing the needed documents, and that in the long run, it will be cost efficient for the jobseekers. She suggested that one important thing that must be done in preparing for the establishment of an OSS is the conduct of consultative meetings among tripartite entities – the workforce, employers, and government.

Interview with BOSS' Clients

Three BOSS's clients agreed to serve as the interviewees for this study. Their experience with the BOSS for business renewal and licensing permits is an added value to this study to know how it is doing and what needs to be improved from the perspective of the end user.

These BOSS's clients claimed that this One Stop Shop's location is very accessible in the sense that all services needed to accomplish the requirements for business permits and renewals are present in one venue, thus, client's movement is made easier. These clients concluded that the BOSS is really better than the old normal practice of applying and transacting the documents for business and licensing permits because the idea of OSS, on the whole, provides them convenience.

The interviewees also provided these suggestions in improving the present BOSS of Caloocan City - South: to digitalize BOSS' transactions, to extend BOSS' operational hours and deadline dates, to increase its quota system to accommodate more clients, and to provide simple needs of clients as in additional chairs. Digitization of transactions is an idea picked up by these clients interviewed from the practice of Valenzuela City.

It is costly for jobseekers to move from one agency to another. On the average, jobseekers have to spare 200 pesos from their personal fund to enable them to apply for those requirements for employment in the six agencies which are found in different locations. The given cost covers only a one-way trip to concerned agencies which means that to go back to these agencies to recover their needed documents will make them spend the same amount.

Long Travel Time

Due to the different locations of the national agencies from whom the jobseekers need to transact for their pre-employment requirements, the respondents of the online survey have revealed that they spend an average of 5-7 hours to move from one agency to the next. This amount of travelling time does not include the time that may necessarily require a jobseeker to go back to any of the concerned agencies. Likewise, neither does it include the time while one lingers in traffic here in Metro Manila.

Enduring the Waiting Period for Transaction Completion

Transacting with the government requires patience. In the jobseekers' experience, they have to allot some two weeks for the transactions they applied for to be completed or accomplished.

From the findings of this study, both the respondents of the online survey and key informant interview gave a resounding affirmation on the idea of establishing an OSS for jobseekers in the LGU of Caloocan-South. From the perspectives of these respondents, the presence of an OSS right within the premises of the city government would resolve, or at the very least, alleviate the difficulties of the jobseekers.

The responses of the jobseekers in the online survey have specifically identified the advantages to be gained when an OSS is built within the city hall grounds.

Accessibility of the place was one helpful advantage recognized by the respondents for it will assist in cutting their travel time and limit their movement from one agency to the next. In addition, their expenses would be lessened. It may, in a way, ease up the transaction process, thus, shorten the waiting period. Overall, the respondents discerned that an OSS for jobseekers would promote convenience and cost efficiency among them.

The foregoing were the same favorable responses of the interviewees on the subject of constituting an OSS for jobseekers. This OSS from these interviewees' point of view would rebound to jobseekers' convenience in securing their pre-employment requirements and the LGU's capacity for an integrated service delivery.

Following the experience of Caloocan's BOSS as solicited from its focal person, the potential of establishing an OSS for jobseekers is possible by ensuring that greater coordination and cooperation between and among partners — the LGU offices and the national agencies involved — must be firmly established. In this manner, the OSS for jobseekers can evolve a system in which the transaction process and corresponding forms are simple, understandable, and less time-consuming.

In addition, it was mentioned by the focal person that consultative meetings among partners and stakeholders must be held prior the establishment of the OSS for jobseekers to serve as clearing house to define functions and responsibilities, and public expectations, including the desirable wants of clients. At the same time, these meetings may help in settling issues among concerned LGU offices and NGAs. These important steps or actions may consequently help in forming the facilitative quality of Caloocan's OSS for jobseekers

Further, the KII with the focal person of Caloocan's BOSS has revealed that the LGU has the capacity to provide the needed resources, such as the available space and current database that could be tapped when the OSS begins to function.

This study tells of the experience of the jobseekers of Caloocan City – South in securing their pre-employment documentary requirements and how this experience was related to

the possibility of establishing a One Stop Shop to facilitate with ease the accomplishments of the said requirements.

Patterns/Trends Obtained from the Findings

The complete data set included the consolidated results of the online survey responded by the 253 jobseekers, the transcript of the interview with the focal person of Caloocan City's BPLO-BOSS, and the transcripts of the interview of three clients of BOSS, who represent their companies when engaging with BOSS in processing their business permits.

The collated data gathered from the jobseekers through the online survey, the researcher found two commonalities:

First, the jobseekers have common concerns as they go about securing their pre-employment requirements. These concerns involved Travel Time and Transaction Period that consumed an average of 2 weeks and 5 to 7 hours, respectively. These may be considered as main contributors to the difficulties being experienced by the jobseekers, aside from the expenses shelled out that amount to an average of P200, only for transportation.

Mankiw (2014) said that "People face trade-offs and rational people think at the margin." This means that trade-offs come with the existence of opportunity cost or the foregone value that jobseekers need to execute because of the inconvenience and inefficiency of government to provide a reliable, fast, and hassle-free approach in providing these clients their pre-employment requirements. Given that time is a scarce resource, improving the efficiency of delivery of services through an OSS, people can maximize the use of their time for other important things.

While "rational people think at the margin" refers to the natural tendency of rational people to determine their current state and look for a viable solution to facilitate and solve their real life difficulties. The respondents' declaration of their difficulty in transacting with government agencies and in travelling to these different agencies gave a clear picture of their situation and it points to the fact that "convenience" is an issue they are facing when securing their much-needed documents. Hence, their answer in the survey affirmed that an OSS for jobseekers could be considered a viable solution.

Second, it is observed from the respondents' answers that they find the idea of OSS as a helpful means for them to secure the pre-employment requirement because it will provide easy accessibility, convenience, and, most of all, it will be cost-efficient.

To the mind of this researcher, people have a natural tendency to think or find a solution to any dilemma being faced or they become accepting of solutions being offered. Following Maslow's (2013) hierarchy of needs of people, the respondents have behaved as such to meet their Security and Safety Need. To acquire their pre-employment requirements in an accessible location that provides them convenience and make them

spend less to satisfy their need and want to be in control of their sense of financial security, health and wellness, and safety. Given the age group of the respondents of the survey, which are 18 years old to 35 years old, they naturally behaved towards Maslow's (2013) second level of hierarchy of needs. The said age group is usually comprised of those population that was prepared or is ready to work or engage in salaried jobs. It is also the age group that is considered to be in their productive life and, therefore, open to actively look for a job that would sufficiently meet their needs for survival and security.

Meanwhile, the findings obtained from the interviews with the key informants have also revealed certain patterns or trends.

First, it was reflected from said interviews that the government is continuously addressing issues that constrain its delivery of services to its constituents. In the case of Caloocan City in this study, the LGU was able to demonstrate its innovative capacity to operate BOSS and further seeks ways to improve this One Stop Shop system. The focal person of BOSS, has humbly admitted certain flaws in the delivery system and other challenges but Caloocan's leadership was always ready to resolve them. This is very much in line with the city's vision of making itself "business- friendly." Having operated BOSS in the last six years, Caloocan City has successfully complied with DILG's directive to all LGUs to provide an accessible and efficient manner to the application and renewal of business licenses.

Second, the three BOSS clients interviewed were one in confirming that Caloocan's BOSS is "good" and a much "improved system than the previous one" (extracted from clients' statements). Moreover, these clients have commented positively about the BOSS workforce. They said that the "staff are knowledgeable and quick to respond, and nice enough to always assist." On the other hand, they gave suggestions on what areas of the BOSS that need improvements, such as longer operational hours, better queuing system, and digitizing the system from filing of application to payment. Overall, these clients were saying that Caloocan's BOSS has successfully satisfied its clients.

Reflecting on the results of the interviews provided the hint that Caloocan City Government appears to be moving towards what is termed as innovation governance (Deschamps, 2013). This author has provided the steps in innovation governance by simply asking the general questions of: "why innovate, how to innovate, how much are you going to innovate, how can you innovate, with whom will you innovate, who is responsible for the innovation." If these questions are answered, it would give an institution a clearer understanding of the whole organization relative to its vision, mission, and goals (or VMG). These VMG leads the institution to know and identify what it wants to achieve as an organization, its vital key players, and its internal and external stakeholders/partners in accomplishing its programs to attain its organizational goals.

Following Deschamps' (2013) thought, this may be the very same idea or principle that guided the Caloocan City Government to roll out BOSS. As gathered from the interview with BOSS' focal person, the establishment of BOSS went through a process. First, a process of examination (assessing the LGU's capability vis-à-vis its mission statement

and available resources, both human and materials). Second, a process of consultation with stakeholders to present the BOSS plan, including its objectives and resource requirements.

Innovation governance, as this researcher understood it from the experience of Caloocan BOSS, is shifting its mindset and governance processes towards introducing innovative initiatives based on its legal mandate and vision for the future in partnership with stakeholders. The LGU has also made BOSS possible by steering its available resources that include sufficient manpower and well-managed database to ensure an efficient service delivery integration. All of these received positive feedback from its clients.

Conclusions

This section has two main parts: (a) restatement of patterns/trends covered in the previous discussion, and (b) the presentation of the final conceptual framework on a One Stop Shop for jobseekers for Caloocan City – South.

This study has brought out these patterns/trends drawn from the respondents' answers to the online survey and interviews conducted. The patterns are as follows:

1. The common difficulties experienced by jobseekers in securing their pre-employment requirements, namely: heavy cost of transportation, long travel time, and enduring the waiting period for transaction completion.
2. Jobseekers' affirmation that a One Stop Shop would be a helpful solution to their difficulties in securing their pre-employment requirements as it will be more accessible, convenient, and cost-efficient.
3. The organizational capability of the city government of Caloocan to practice innovation governance as demonstrated in the processes taken to establish BOSS (Business One Stop Shop).
4. Caloocan City Government's exercise of innovation governance is affirmed by its constituents/clients that includes the LGU's resoluteness to further improve and innovate.

Given all the learnings gained by this researcher from the whole research process, this section closes with the presentation of the final conceptual framework for a One Stop Shop for jobseekers.

The following Figure 2 shows the revised conceptual framework that provides for a preparatory phase or stage prior the operation of an OSS for jobseekers. This Preparatory Stage is represented as a cycle and the stages involved are defined to show the steps in preparing for the establishment of the OSS. The consideration for these stages were drawn from the experience of Caloocan's BOSS as exemplified by its focal person.

The first stage is centered on reviewing the relevant laws and policies covering the establishment of an OSS for jobseekers. Stage 2 is initiating coordination work with the Department of Labor and Employment for clearer guidelines on the implementing rules

and regulation for an OSS for jobseekers. Stage 3 is the conduct of consultative meetings with the six NGAs charged with processing and releasing of pre-employment documents. It is also at this stage that the LGU and the six NGAs can negotiate on necessary provisions and assistance that is expected to produce the coordinate mechanism of these government institutions that will bring about a more integrated system of delivering needed services by the jobseekers. Stage 4 is the period in which the LGU reviews its current capacity to complement the needed provisions and resources negotiated in Stage 3 and most of all, its operational capacity to launch another OSS. It is also at this stage when the LGU defines the system and rules governing the affairs of the OSS. The last stage is the institutionalization of PESO and eventual assignment to spearhead the establishment of the OSS for jobseekers and lead in its year-round operation. The cyclical presentation of this Preparatory Stage is to illustrate that each stage occurs for the purpose of achieving its target or expected output/s, but it can recur at any given interval. This is to give the chance to check and recheck any lapses committed in any given stage of preparation. A cyclical process could mean continuing improvement that this study hopes to make if ever this conceptual framework is adopted.

Figure 2.0
Final Conceptual Framework for an OSS for Jobseekers: A Proposal

Recommendations

Today, time and cost are not solely the focus of any government project but also the accessibility of government services to the public, especially considering the different externalities that its citizens are experiencing such as heaviness of traffic in the metropolis, inflation rate, problem of safety, inconveniences, unemployment rate, and many others. In this context, this researcher believes that establishing an OSS that will facilitate an easier manner by which jobseekers are able to secure their pre-employment requirements must be made a priority of an LGU, like Caloocan City- South.

In line with the foregoing, herewith are recommendations that may pave the ground for establishing an OSS for jobseekers in Caloocan City – South.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adheres with ethical research practices, the data used in the study conform to the Philippine Data Privacy Act of 2013 (RA 10173), which establishes guidelines for the collection, handling, and dissemination of data. The study complies with national data sharing regulations. The structured methodological approach ensures the transparency, accountability, and integrity of data analysis throughout the research process.

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